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Academic Self- Efficacy As A Correlate Of Academic Procrastination Among Public Secondary School Students In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined academic self-efficacy as a correlate of academic procrastination among public secondary school students (SS2) in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 3,387 senior secondary school two (SSII) students in sixty-five (65) public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. The population comprised 1422 male students and 1965 female students. The sample of the study was 358 (male and female) secondary school students from the 65 public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. A multistage sampling technique was employed to determine the sample of the study. The instruments for data collection were two instruments: Academic Procrastination Scale (APS) and Self-Efficacy for Learning (SEL) Questionnaire. The instruments were both adapted by the researcher and were submitted to three experts in the faculty of Education for re-validation. Pearson Product Moment Correlational analysis and multiple regression were used to analyze the data for the study. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant moderate negative relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination. Also, there was a significant moderate negative relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female students. The researcher concludes based on the findings of the study that academic self-efficacy has moderate negative relationship with academic procrastination among SS2 students in public secondary schools in Awka education zone of Anambra State. Based on these findings, it was recommended among others that teachers should teach in a way that would capture the interests of the SS2 students. It was also recommended that SS2 Students in Awka education zone of Anambra State, should be provided with conducive and supportive study environment that promotes consistent study habits and autonomy

Keywords: academic self-efficacy, procrastination, students

INTRODUCTION

Secondary school is the developmental stage in the lives of students where academic habits are solidified and future educational trajectories are significantly influenced. One of the habits developed by students is academic procrastination. Some students begin to procrastinate as life's challenges get tougher as they move up the academic ladder (from primary to secondary, secondary to university). Such challenges require individuals to possess certain characteristics or qualities, including high level of determination, self- monitoring as well as self -starting capacity. Mbathia (2018), opined that education can provide

individuals with those characteristics as well as explicit skills such as developing learning strategies, self-efficacy and self-regulated learning methods, which enable them to perform specific tasks successfully and efficiently. As they get better in performing their tasks, they become better motivated and more competitive to perform better in future. As the students struggle to perform better, one notable variable that besets students' academic performance is academic procrastination.

Academic procrastination is certainly not a new phenomenon. It has existed for much of history and continues to thrive in modern era. Academic Procrastination is a common practice in general as well as among students. Steel (2017), defined academic procrastination as "the irrational delay of actions despite expecting to be worse off for the delay" within the academic context. Academic procrastination is a special form of procrastination that occurs in the academic settings. It involves knowing that one needs to carry-out an academic task or undertake an academic activity such as writing term-paper, studying for exams, finishing a school related project or undertaking the weekly reading assignments but for one reason or another failing to motivate oneself to do so within the expected time frame (Ackerman & Gross, 2019).

Academic procrastination is the tendency to put off or delay school-related tasks and activities. Students procrastinate when they delay a task or use excuses to justify delay in doing an academic activity. Academic Procrastination can also be viewed as failing to perform an academic activity within a desired time frame or postponing until the last minute, activities one needs to be completed (Wolters, 2018). According to the researcher, academic procrastination is the act of unnecessarily delaying or postponing school related tasks despite knowing that there could be negative consequences for doing so. It is the practice of doing more pleasurable tasks or carrying out less urgent academic tasks instead of more urgent academic works, thus putting off impending tasks to a later time. Academic procrastination is similar to general procrastination, in that, it is negatively related to self-efficacy and life satisfaction and also positively related to stress and mental health. One notable variable among others that has been linked to academic procrastination especially in the developed world, is academic self-efficacy.

Efficacy is synonymous with the term effective, efficacious, control. Self is defined as the identity of a person. Bandura (2015) defined self-efficacy as "the belief in one's capacity to organize and execute the course of action required to manage prospective situations, it is personal assessments about one's competence to complete a task". Self-efficacy has been defined in a variety of ways, but Bandura defines it as a combination of self-confidence, self-reliance and self-trust. Self-efficacy is concerned with how well a person believes they will be able to achieve a desired objective in a specific area. Blascovich and Tomaka (2018) viewed academic self-efficacy as a student's sense of his or her value or worth, or the extent to which a student values, approves of, appreciates, prizes, or likes his or herself. Academic self-efficacy is multidimensional, that is, domain specific or context dependent. This means that high sense of self-efficacy in a particular domain may not necessarily translate in to having similar level in another domain. Even within the same domain, there may be different levels of self-efficacy beliefs occurring in various contexts. In the academic setting, many studies have shown that there is a positive relation between self-efficacy and academic procrastination. Studies found that regardless of age, gender, domains, disciplines and countries, a student with higher sense of academic self-efficacy will achieve better academic performance. Louis and Mistele (2019) reported that although there were differences in level of academic self-efficacy by gender in young adolescents taking economics and science, academic self-efficacy is still found to be a good predictor of academic procrastination. Amil (2020) studied the academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of students taking economics at 'A' level and found that there was a significant, positive correlation between academic self-efficacy with academic procrastination. Liem et al (2018) examined academic self-efficacy, task value and performance goals in English language ability with a group of secondary school students. It is found that self-efficacy is a predictor to English test scores. Purzer (2021) did a sequential mixed methods study to examine the relationship between team discourse, academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination. Results showed that academics self-efficacy is positively and significantly correlated with academic procrastination. In most of the studies the level of self-efficacy is found to be different between genders.

However, this has not been empirically proven to be the case in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is against this backdrop that the present study was conducted:

Statement of the Problem

Academic success among secondary school students is shaped by a range of psychological, social, and cognitive factors. Among these, academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination have been identified as key psychological variables influencing students' learning behaviours and academic achievement. Academic self-efficacy affects students' motivation, persistence, and ability to cope with academic challenges, whereas academic procrastination is associated with delayed task completion, poor performance, and heightened stress and anxiety.

Empirical evidence indicates that many secondary school students engage in procrastinatory behaviours, often linked to low academic self-efficacy. Students who lack confidence in their academic abilities are more likely to delay tasks as a means of avoiding failure or managing anxiety. This pattern can create a negative cycle in which procrastination further weakens self-efficacy, resulting in declining academic outcomes and reduced academic confidence. Despite this theoretical relationship, empirical studies within secondary school contexts remain limited, particularly in settings characterised by large class sizes, inadequate individualised attention, and insufficient psychological support.

Furthermore, existing research has largely concentrated on university and college students, with limited attention given to secondary school students, whose academic attitudes and behaviours are still developing and highly adaptable. This gap is notable, as adolescence represents a critical stage for the formation of lasting academic habits. Although some studies have examined academic self-efficacy and procrastination, few have explored their relationship using gender and residential mode as moderating variables within the education zone of the present study. Consequently, this study seeks to examine the correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination among secondary school students in the study area, thereby addressing this identified research gap.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine academic self-efficacy as a correlate of academic procrastination among secondary school students in Awka education zone of Anambra state.

Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of SS2 students in Awka education zone of Anambra state.
2. Examine the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female SS2 students in Awka education zone of Anambra state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of SS2 students?
2. What is the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female SS2 students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of SS2 students in Awka education zone of Anambra state.
2. There is no significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female SS2 students in Awka education zone of Anambra state.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted a correlational research design to examine the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination among public secondary school students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State, Nigeria. The study area comprises five Local Government Areas with 65 public secondary schools and was selected due to persistent concerns about students' procrastinatory behaviours

despite the high value placed on education. The population consisted of 3,387 SS2 students (1,422 males and 1,965 females) in the 2024/2025 academic session, from which a sample size of 358 was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed, involving stratified, simple random, and cluster sampling techniques, resulting in the selection of five co-educational secondary schools and ten SS2 arms, with 400 students participating to accommodate attrition.

Data were collected using two adapted instruments: the 26-item Self-Efficacy for Learning (SEL) questionnaire and the 25-item Academic Procrastination Scale (APS), both rated on a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree (SA)-A, Agree (A)-3, Disagree (D)-2 and Strongly Disagree (D)-1). The instruments were validated by three experts in education and their internal consistency was established using Cronbach Alpha, yielding reliability coefficients of 0.965 for the SEL and 0.971 for the APS. Data were collected through direct administration of questionnaires, with 322 properly completed copies returned, representing an 89.9% response rate. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses 1 and 2 at the 0.05 level of significance, with data analysed using SPSS version 26. Correlation coefficients were interpreted based on established guidelines, and hypothesis decisions were made using p-values, where values less than or equal to 0.05 indicated statistical significance.

RESULT

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State?*

Table 1. Pearson’s Correlation between Academic Self-efficacy and Academic Procrastination of SS2 Students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State (n=322)

Variables	N	Academic efficacy	Self- Academic Procrastination	Remark
Academic self-efficacy	322	1	-0.38	Moderate Negative
Academic procrastination	322	-0.38	1	

Table 1 presented the Pearson’s correlation (r) between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination among SS2 students in Awka Education zone of Anambra state. This yielded a correlation coefficient of -0.38 which suggested that there was a moderate negative correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination among SS2 students. This implied that an increase in academic self-efficacy results in a decrease in academic procrastination at a moderate degree.

Research Question Two: *What is the relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State?*

Table 2. Pearson’s Correlation between Academic Self-efficacy and Academic Procrastination of Male and Female SS2 Students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State.

Variables	N	Academic efficacy	Self- Academic Procrastination	Remark
Male:				
Academic self-efficacy	146	1	-0.39	Moderate Negative
Academic procrastination	146	-0.39	1	
Female:				
Academic self-efficacy	176	1	-0.38	Moderate Negative
Academic procrastination	176	-0.38	1	

Table 2 showed the Pearson’s correlation (r) between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination based on gender of SS2 students in Awka Education zone of Anambra state. Among the male students, correlation coefficient obtained was -0.39 while -0.38 was obtained for the female sample. This indicated a moderate negative correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination. However, the negative correlation was slightly stronger among male SS2 students in Awka Education zone of Anambra state.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State.

Table 5

Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation Between Academic Self-efficacy and Academic Procrastination of SS2 Students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State (n=322)

Variables	N	Academic efficacy	Self- Academic Procrastination	P	Remark
Academic self-efficacy	322	1	-0.38	0.000	Significant
Academic procrastination	322	-0.38	1		

Table 5 shows that there was a significant negative correlation between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination among SS2 students in Awka Education of Anambra state, $r = -0.38$, $p = 0.000$. The p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State.

Table 6. Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Academic Self-efficacy and Academic Procrastination of Male and Female SS2 Students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State

Variables	N	Academic efficacy	Self- Procrastination	P	Remark
<i>Male:</i>					
Academic self-efficacy	146	1	-0.39	0.000	Significant
Academic procrastination	146	-0.39	1		
<i>Female:</i>					
Academic self-efficacy	176	1	-0.38	0.000	Significant
Academic procrastination	176	-0.38	1		

As shown in Table 6, there was a significant negative relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination among male SS2 students, $r = -0.39$, $p = 0.000$. Similarly, there was a significant negative relationship between the two variables among female SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra state, $r = -0.38$, $p = 0.000$. Since the p-values were less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected.

DISCUSSION

The finding of this study revealed that there was a moderate negative relationship between the academic procrastination and academic self-efficacy of SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. This means that when students procrastinate in their academics, they experience a downward spiral in their academic self-efficacy. It also means that whenever they have a high academic self-efficacy, they procrastinate less. This is in line with the findings of Steel, (2017); Chu & Choi, (2020); Rajani, (2018) where it was observed that the tendency to procrastinate decreases when students’ self-efficacy belief about their solving difficult problems increases. One possible explanation for the moderate negative relationship is that procrastination is a multidimensional behaviour influenced by several personal, emotional, and environmental factors beyond academic self-efficacy. While students who believe in their academic capabilities are generally more motivated to begin and complete tasks on time, other factors such as personality traits, poor time-management skills, anxiety, fear of failure, and lack of interest may still contribute to academic procrastination. These additional influences may reduce the overall strength of the relationship. Furthermore, students with higher academic self-efficacy may be less prone to avoidance behaviour, as they tend to perceive academic tasks as manageable and achievable. This reduces the likelihood of delaying academic work. Conversely, students with low self-efficacy often view assignments as overwhelming or too difficult, prompting them to postpone tasks as a coping mechanism (Tice and Bratslasky, 2019). This pattern helps explain the negative direction of the relationship found in the study. However, the correlation was only moderate because not all students with high self-efficacy necessarily avoid procrastination. Some may delay academic tasks due to overconfidence, believing they can complete assignments quickly at a later time. Others may be habitual procrastinators or engage in academic procrastination for reasons unrelated to confidence, such as lack of time-management skills, competing responsibilities, or a preference for working under pressure. These tendencies weaken the strength of the relationship. The findings may also reflect contextual and cultural factors within the Awka

Education Zone. SS2 Students may face environmental challenges such as heavy academic workload, limited access to study materials, or domestic responsibilities that contribute to academic procrastination regardless of their self-efficacy levels. Peer influence and school-related pressures may likewise moderate the link between confidence and timely task completion.

This finding further indicated that there was a significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic self-efficacy of SS2 students in Awka Education zone of Anambra state, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Academic procrastination might be as a result of lack of individualized attention or poor psychological support by teachers leading to a decline in their academic self-efficacy. The practices of some teachers like focusing on the intelligent students and leaving the dull ones to sought themselves out or even mocking them during classes because of questions answered wrongly, can lead the students to have a decline in their academic self-efficacy which might lead them to skip their classes and avoid assignments because they would not want a repeat of the embarrassment that resulted from the mockery from the teacher. Such students would sought for ways to just pass and if these ways were not found they become frustrated and experience a decline in their academic self-efficacy leading to academic procrastination and then dropout.

The finding of this study revealed that there is a moderate negative relationship between the academic procrastination and academic self-efficacy of male and female SS2 students in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. However, the negative relationship was slightly stronger among male SS2 students. This result suggested that male students' academic procrastination behaviours are more sensitive to their level of academic self-efficacy than female students. In other words male students with low academic self-efficacy are more likely to procrastinate than female students with similar low academic self-efficacy. This means that when male SS2 students have high self-efficacy, they tend to procrastinate less than females with the same level of academic self-efficacy. This finding is line with Van Eerde (2018), who stated that males are slightly more likely to procrastinate than females. Steel (2017), and Ferrari (2019) found procrastination more common in males than females. One possible explanation for the moderate negative relationship in both groups is that academic self-efficacy consistently serves as a motivational factor across genders, helping students to initiate and complete academic tasks more promptly. Students, whether male or female who believe they can succeed academically are less inclined to delay assignments because they perceive academic challenges as manageable rather than threatening. Conversely, those with low academic self-efficacy tend to procrastinate due to fear of failure, avoidance tendencies, or feelings of incompetence. The slightly stronger relationship observed among male students may be attributed to gender differences in confidence expression, help-seeking behaviour, and task-avoidance tendencies. Research indicated that males often display higher academic self-confidence, even when their actual performance is comparable to that of females. Thus, increase in academic self-efficacy may have a more pronounced effect on reducing academic procrastination among male students, as they may rely more heavily on personal confidence when approaching academic tasks.

Another possible reason is that male students may be more prone to behavioural procrastination, which is directly linked to motivation and academic self-efficacy. When their academic self-efficacy improves, this behavioural procrastination reduces noticeably (Ferrari, 2019). Female students, on the other hand, may also experience emotional forms of procrastination, rooted in anxiety, perfectionism, or fear of disappointing others. Such factors influence academic procrastination independently of academic self-efficacy, making the correlation slightly weaker for females. The finding may also reflect differences on how male and female students respond to academic stress. Male students may depend more on task-oriented coping strategies, making academic self-efficacy a strong determinant of whether they procrastinate. Female students often combine task-oriented and emotion-oriented strategies; thus, even when they are confident academically, emotional factors may still lead to delays in task completion. Despite these slight gender differences, the moderate nature of the relationships for both groups suggests that academic self-efficacy is important but not the sole factor influencing academic procrastination. Time-management skills, peer influence, school environment, and personal habits also play significant roles for both genders. Overall, the findings indicated that while academic self-efficacy contributes to

reducing academic procrastination for both male and female students, its impact is somewhat more pronounced among males.

The findings of this study further indicated that there was a significant negative relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination of male and female SS2 students and hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This might be as a result of certain underlying psychological factors like motivation, confidence, self-regulation, and academic pressure, which affect both genders in comparable ways. This is in line with Klassen (2019) findings where it was observed that the tendency to procrastinate decreases when students' self-efficacy belief increases.

CONCLUSION

The researcher concludes based on the findings of the study that academic self-efficacy has moderate negative relationship with academic procrastination among SS2 students in public secondary schools in Awka education zone of Anambra State. The findings revealed a significant inverse relationship between academic procrastination and academic self-efficacy, indicating that increased procrastination is associated with reduced self-efficacy, while higher levels of academic self-efficacy correspond with lower procrastination tendencies. This pattern was consistent across both male and female students, demonstrating that procrastination adversely affects students' confidence in their academic abilities regardless of gender. Overall, the study concludes that strengthening students' academic self-efficacy may play a critical role in reducing procrastinatory behaviours and improving academic outcomes among secondary school students in the study area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study and their educational implications, the following recommendations were proffered.

1. School managements should organize orientation for SS2 students from time to time to talk on academic self-efficacy and give ways on how to boost it and also on risks involved in academic procrastination and ways to reduce it.
2. Guidance and counsellors should help on counselling procrastinating male SS2 students so they can complete their work in due time. They can do this by hinting on the detrimental effect of academic procrastination and how it can reduce their academic self-efficacy. They should also look out for those already suffering from low academic self-efficacy and find ways to boost it.

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